

Comparing classification algorithms in predicting COVID19 deaths

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Abstract

In this work we compare a number of classification algorithms in predicting COVID19 deaths. We combine data from a number of different datasets in the Vivli database and we demonstrate that while classic algorithms perform well in terms of accuracy, if one wants to increase the specificity it needs to treat the imbalance in the number of observations between the two classes. In almost all the cases improving specificity has a small cost in the overall accuracy.

1 Introduction

First reported in Wuhan, China, at the end of 2019 [20], the world was exposed to an unprecedented disease, now known as COVID-19 or SARS-CoV-2 (severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2). COVID-19 is a part of a large family of viruses known as coronaviruses, which attack the respiratory system [25]. Coronaviruses can cause a range of illnesses from a common cold to more serious infections resulting in hospitalisation and sometimes death. This deadly virus of COVID-19 made its way around the world. In the UK as of 30 June 2022, 904,639 people were hospitalised within the first 28 days of a positive test, 177,977 deaths were recorded on the same timeline, [9]. Worldwide, there have been 6.36 million deaths reported along with 558 million cases, as recorded by “Our World in Data” [15].

In order to reduce the the hospitalisation rate and death rate, it is essential to understand the demographic of the population who are most at risk. For example, a study [6] has shown that men are more likely to have a lower resilience to infections than women, including the coronavirus infection. In this project, we aim to predict the outcome of those infected by COVID-19 based upon their demographic information. In doing such, we focus on the

use of machine Learning (ML) classification algorithms - a popular mathematical tool used increasingly within healthcare. ML algorithms are able to work with large data sets to group data into various categories. This is utilised in many ways within medicine, including classifying severity of diseases based upon medical records, or, in our case, understanding which patients may be more likely to die, or survive, from COVID-19, based upon their demographic information.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. In Section 2 we present a small literature review, then we discuss an overview of the methodology we will compare in Section 3 and the numerical experiments in Section 4. We close with a discussion at the end.

2 Related work

There is an abundance of work available in the literature which have been published since COVID-19 was declared a pandemic. Here we present a small selection (which is by no means exhaustive) of studies which were published and use classification and prediction algorithms.

In [7] the authors used regression and ARIMA models to predict deaths in the UK, while in [3] they use classification algorithms to predict deaths in South Korea. The authors in [24] explored using ARIMA models, similar to that of [7], in order to predict the spread of COVID-19 in 15 different countries, including Spain, Italy, Germany, United States and the UK. Moreover, the authors in [13] looked in using artificial neural networks (ANN) to model cases and deaths of COVID-19, based upon data from the World Health Organisation (WHO). They use different metrics (mean square error, mean absolute error etc) to evaluate the performance.

A further study in [4] assessed the effectiveness of using biomarker measurements when predicting outcomes of COVID-19. Interestingly, it was seen that the simple features such as age and National Early Warning Score (NEWS2), worked as better predictor variables than the biomarker information, when comparing the performance. We will see similar observations in our studies. Using commodities to predict the outcome of COVID-19 patients has also been explored in [5] where it was found that the elderly population more frequently suffered with hypertension, diabetes and coronary heart disease, but was unsure whether these proved to be a risk factor. They concluded that some commodities can be seen as their own risk factor, with 59.6% of the patients within their study that died to have had hypertension, and 29.4% with a history of falls or fragility. There is also the work

by [18] where the authors looked at using machine learning ridge logistic regression with LASSO variable selection to investigate various factors influencing COVID-19 transmissibility and deaths. Age and sex were seen to be significantly associated with COVID-19.

3 Methodology to compare

In the literature there is an abundance of classification methodology that one can use to create classification rules. It is always a challenge to decide what are the most appropriate to use when comparing performance. Using the recommendation in [10] where it is claimed that choosing some algorithms from different classes of classification methodology allow us to have a clear picture of the best solution available. Therefore, in this work we will use one algorithm from the families of Logistic regression (LR), of Support Vector Machines (SVM) algorithm, of Random Forest (RF) and of a decision tree. As we will see in the numerical section in some cases we also introduced some variants as well of the methodology to address some of the problems in performance that appear. In this section we will quickly give the basic algorithms we will describe in the numerical studies.

3.1 Logistic regression

Logistic Regression (LR) is a classification technique based on the idea of linear regression when the response variable is categorical. Due to our dependant outcome variable being binary (0/1 Death/Survival), we can categorise the type of LR into Binary Logistic Regression (BLR) and this is what differs between Linear and Logistic regression - the ability to include dichotomous dependent variables (variables with only two categories).

The equation of a simple logistic regression model to estimate the probability of an event occurring takes the form,

$$p = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-X\theta}} \quad (1)$$

and one can show that the '*Sigmoid Function*' converts all values from the linear regression into probabilities, ensuring all values are now in the interval [0,1]. [12]

Regression analysis allows us to predict outcomes of our dependant variable based upon multiple independent variables and their interactions, as well as understand the independent variable's degree of impact. In order to use regression analysis within our study, we will look at demographic

information of interest alongside the overall outcome of the patient. For example, is there a relationship between a patients Age, Sex, Ethnicity or Race and their overall outcome after hospital admission, this being discharge or death. Logistic regression has been used in the past in medical related research. See for example [11] where the authors demonstrate the use of logistic regression in predicting hospital mortality rates based upon admission laboratory tests and age.

3.2 Support Vector Machine

A very well known and frequently used classification technique is the *Support Vector Machines* (SVM) ([8]). Formally, given a labeled training data set:

$$(x_1, y_1), \dots, (x_n, y_n), x_i \in R^d \text{ and } y_i \in (-1, +1)$$

where x_i is a feature vector representation and y_i the class label of the i^{th} observation. Then, the optimal hyperplane is defined as:

$$wx^T + b = 0$$

where w is the normal vector, x is the input vector, and b is the offset. Furthermore, in the simplest case where the data are separated, w and b must satisfy:

$$wx_i^T + b \geq +1 \text{ if } y_i = +1, \text{ and } wx_i^T + b \leq -1 \text{ if } y_i = -1.$$

In many cases there are many pairs of (w, b) that satisfy the above constraints, but SVM will find w and b such that $1/\|w\|^2$ (a quantity known as the margin) is maximised and this process is known as the hard margin classifier. In the most general case, the soft margin SVM classifier allows for misclassifications where the constraints are

$$wx_i^T + b \geq +1 - \xi_i \text{ if } y_i = +1, \text{ and } wx_i^T + b \leq -1 + \xi_i \text{ if } y_i = -1.$$

and we minimize the function

$$\|w\|^2 + \lambda \sum_{i=1}^n \xi_i$$

where λ is a tuning parameter known as the misclassification penalty and ξ_i are slack variables denoting the misclassification distance (it gets a value 0 when the point associated with it is correctly classified and a positive value when the point is incorrectly classified).

SVM have been used in numerous applications and have been extended in a number of directions. The work in [8] which introduced the idea has been cited around 25000 times so far. One example with application to a medical application is the work in [17] where the authors are working on classifying types of diabetes using SVM and the work in [19] where the authors has compared the use of SVM against logistic regression models on a variety of data sets and a variety of settings including the discussion of imbalanced datasets. It was shown that logistic regression is more biased than SVM towards the majority class when we have imbalanced.

Now, to remove the bias of SVM due to the imbalance of the two classes a number of methods have been introduced in the literature. For an extensive review, the reader can look into [2]. One of the most successful methods and probably one of the simplest is to use different misclassification penalty for each one of the two classes. Following the advice from [1] we choose the two costs approach which takes the ratio of the costs as the inverse ratio of the class sizes, that is $\lambda_1/\lambda_2 = n_2/n_1$. For simplicity we denote with λ_1, n_1 the cost and sample size associated with the class which has the majority of observations and we set $\lambda_2 = 1$.

3.3 Decision trees

Decision trees are a classification technique used to predict the probability/likelihood of an event happening and a useful visualization method.

Decision trees are a combination of nodes, leaf nodes, and branches between the two type of nodes. The nodes in our tree test the data for certain true or false criteria, and the branches show the possible results of the test, ultimately resulting in our final leaf nodes, predicting the final outcome. There are multiple types of decision trees, including classification and regression. Classification trees have a series of ‘Yes/No’ response questions on categorical (discrete) data. Binary recursive partition is an iterative process used to split the data into partitions and branches of a tree in order to reach a classified outcome. This means the data is repeatedly split into small subsets until specified stopping criterion has been met. Whereas, regression trees are useful when our variable of interest is a continuous data type. For our study, we are aiming to classify whether patients have died or survived after COVID-19 infection, therefore we will use classification trees due to the fact our target variable is binary/categorical.

There are many practical applications of decision trees within the medical industry. For example, the authors in [23] has looked at using decision trees in order to categorise the severity of COVID-19 symptoms. They

compared trees and confirmed that by using the decision tree, you could draw clear results as to if someone is exposed to mild, moderate or severe COVID-19. Advantages of classification with decision trees include that it is a relatively simple and inexpensive method producing results that are visual, and therefore easy to interpret for small trees. However, some drawbacks include how larger trees can be more difficult to draw conclusions from as well as easily overfitting the data. Another example is [21] where the authors discuss how decision trees are a useful classification technique within medicine, especially within medical diagnostics. They emphasises the importance of how decision support systems play a big role when helping physicians within the healthcare environment.

3.4 Random forests

Random forests (RF) is a more general methodology than a decision tree. A 'Forest' refers to many decision trees, trained together under the assumption that the combination of multiple models will ultimately improve the overall result, known as the 'bagging' method. The improved result aims to increase accuracy and stability of the final predictions.

RFs have been used in a number of medical studies including the work in [26] where the authors try to classify diabetic patients on the type of diabetes they have. In [14] the authors investigate different methods of tuning the random forest parameters in order to increase the accuracy of the classification. RF algorithms are also known to deal well with imbalanced data sets. The authors in [16] explore the use of random forest compared with SVM for a classifying disease such as breast cancer with highly imbalanced data.

4 Numerical Studies

In this section we will present the numerical studies for the comparison of the methods. We will start with exploratory analysis of the data and we will then try to measure the classification performance of the aforementioned algorithms.

We will use the following metrics:

- accuracy based on the percentage of correct prediction (those who died and those who survived over all the number of subjects)
- specificity which is the percentage of correct prediction of those who survived

- sensitivity which is the percentage of correct prediction of those who died
- precision which is the those that were correctly predicted to survive over all the people who were predicted to survive (correctly or incorrectly)
- F1 score which has the formula $2 * \text{Sensitivity} * \text{Precision} / (\text{Sensitivity} + \text{Precision})$.

4.1 Data source/collection

Our analysis is based on data collected through the Vivli platform. This comes with a couple of challenges as there were a number of different sources Vivli collected the data and therefore there are differences between the sources both in the way things are collected as well as the variables being collected. The biggest challenge is probably the missing data which we have to impute before performing our analysis.

4.2 Exploratory Data Analysis

Variable	Overall, N = 2,129	Died, N = 403	Survived, N = 1,726
Sex			
<i>Female</i>	791 (37%)	132 (33%)	659 (38%)
<i>Male</i>	1,338 (68%)	271 (67%)	1,067 (62%)
<i>No. Missing Data</i>	0	0	0
Age (years)			
<i>Median (25%, 75%)</i>	60.0 (49.0, 69.0)	67.0 (60.0, 74.0)	58.0 (48.0, 67.0)
<i>Minimum</i>	15.0	20.0	15.0
<i>Maximum</i>	95.0	90.0	95.0
<i>No. Missing Data</i>	14	5	9
Ethnicity			
<i>Hispanic or Latino</i>	1,005 (47%)	201 (50%)	804 (47%)
<i>Not Hispanic or Latino</i>	1,059 (50%)	181 (45%)	878 (51%)
<i>Not Reported</i>	38 (1.8%)	15 (3.7%)	23 (1.3%)
<i>Unknown</i>	27 (1.3%)	6 (1.5%)	21 (1.2%)
<i>No. Missing Data</i>	0	0	0
Race			
<i>Asian</i>	96 (4.5%)	10 (2.5%)	86 (5.0%)
<i>Black or African American</i>	284 (13%)	55 (14%)	229 (13%)
<i>Multiple</i>	19 (0.9%)	6 (1.5%)	13 (0.8%)
<i>Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander</i>	26 (1.2%)	4 (1.0%)	22 (1.3%)
<i>Unknown</i>	313 (15%)	63 (16%)	250 (14%)
<i>White</i>	1,391 (65%)	265 (66%)	1,126 (65%)
<i>No. Missing Data</i>	0	0	0
BMI (kg/m²)			
<i>Median (25%, 75%)</i>	30.6 (26.1, 36.3)	30.3 (26.6, 34.8)	30.7 (26.0, 36.4)
<i>Minimum</i>	12.8	12.8	14.1
<i>Maximum</i>	81.0	70.9	81.0
<i>No. Missing Data</i>	1,179	271	908
Height (cm)			
<i>Median (25%, 75%)</i>	168.0 (160.0, 175.0)	167.0 (160.0, 175.3)	168.0 (160.3, 175.0)
<i>Minimum</i>	133.0	149.0	133.0
<i>Maximum</i>	211.0	188.0	211.0
<i>No. Missing Data</i>	1,308	284.0	1,024
Weight (kg)			
<i>Median (25%, 75%)</i>	89.0 (76.2, 104.2)	87.0 (74.1, 100.0)	89.2 (77.0, 105.0)
<i>Minimum</i>	40.0	40.0	44.0
<i>Maximum</i>	279.9	163.7	279.9
<i>No. Missing Data</i>	641	130	511

Table 1: Data summary table

In Table 1, we can see a summary of our complete study data. In bold on the left hand side of the table, we see the variables chosen to begin our analysis, and summary statistics across the columns, separated into groups based on survival.

In our analysis, there are some aspects that should be initially highlighted, for example, we do not have an even divide of male and female patients when all six studies are combined. From our literature review, we are aware how COVID-19 has been shown to have a more adverse impact on male patients when compared to females. We can infer from our summary that out of our 1338 male patients, 20% died, compared to 17% of the female participants. Despite an unequal proportion of male to female participants, our data still follows a similar story to that of [6].

Overall, our combined study has a large range of ages, spanning from 15 to 95 years, with a median of 60. The average age of those who died during

the study is 67 years, being 7 years older than the overall median age, as well as being 9 years older than the median age of those who survived, at 58. It is obvious that an increased age has negatively affected the survival rates, and this can be seen in our data in Table 1.

4.3 Missing Data

We can also see from Table 1, that there are variables with large portions of missing data, for example there are 1308 participants with missing height data. Before beginning our analysis we need to deal with any missing data. As we have collected data from a variety of different studies, the quantity and level is different for every study we have included, therefore we do have some sections with missing data.

Figure 1: Showing amount of missing data over all studies.

Figure 1 is a visual representation of the missing values for each variable in the full data set. With variables along the horizontal axis and observations on the vertical axis, the black illustrates the missing observations for each variable, whereas the grey is values present. We know that overall, there is 16.4% missing within our data set. We can see in Figure 1 that there is a high proportion of missing data for Weight, Height and BMI. The easiest way deal with this would be to remove these patient's data from our analysis. However, if we removed all participants with missing values, our data frame would more than half in size, resulting in less accurate and reliable results. Therefore, we will have to deal with these missing data points in a different way in order to maintain as many patients in the analysis as possible. We can take a closer look into where the data is missing from in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Showing amount of missing data per study. The x- axis although unlabelled give us an indication of the percentage of missing values of each variable in each study.

Figure 2 shows the spread of missing values across the 6 individual studies in our analysis. We can see a high proportion of our missing values of Height, Weight and BMI originate from studies 4 and 5. If we remove these studies from our analysis, our sample size will decrease massively from 2129 participants to 1028, again by over a half. Therefore, removing these studies or the individual participants with missing data are not helpful methods to deal with missing values in our analysis.

Figure 3: Imputation method comparison for weight. On the y-axis we report relative frequency

We look at using some powerful R packages in order to impute estimates of the missing values. We have compared the use of *missForest* against *MICE* packages in R. In Figure 3 we can see histograms of the distribution of weight before imputation and then with the use of *missForest* and *MICE*. We can see that there is a difference between how the packages predict the missing weight data, especially around 100lbs. *MICE* seems to be doing a slightly better job at maintaining the proportion of people imputed with lower and upper values although the differences are very small.

4.4 Classification results

In order to run the classification algorithms we split the data into 70% training and 30% testing. The response variable (also known as label variable in

the classification literature is the indicator variable whether the person has died or not (0 means survived and 1 that they died)

4.4.1 Logistic Regression

We first start with logistic regression where fit the model using seven variables as predictors. Those are: age, sex, race, ethnicity, weight, height and BMI. The model aims to predict the likelihood of death of a patient based upon their demographic data, taking the following form:

$$Death \sim Age + Sex + Race + Ethnicity + Weight + Height + BMI \quad (2)$$

After fitting the model to the training data set, we can assess the model's predictive ability on the testing data set. If the probability of the output is greater than 0.5 then we classify the subject as one of those who died, otherwise if it is less than 0.5 then we classify the subject as a survived one.

When first running the model, we can see that the model classifies patients with **80.9%** accuracy, which at first glance seems to be good, with only **19.1%** miss-classified. However, when taking a closer look into the miss-classification, we can see that only **2.2%** of those who died were correctly classified, which is an extremely low specificity. In order to increase this specificity, we look further in to re-running the model with weighting our classes due to the imbalance, i.e there is a higher proportion of individuals who survived in the dataset than individuals who died. By adding a higher weight to the 'died' class, we will hopefully be able to predict those who died with a higher specificity as they are seen as the more important class to correctly classify. Continuing with the weighted model, based on the number of observations and the new results are summarized in Table ??.

After introducing the class weightings to the model, our overall accuracy has decreased slightly from **80.9%** to **75.4%**, however, the specificity of classifying those who died has increased from a **2.2%** to **29.2%**. Although not particularly high, it is still an improved specificity for our model, which is important when predicting those who die.

Training Set	Testing Set
Accuracy	Accuracy
= $(1054 + 87) / 1492 = \mathbf{76.5\%}$	= $(445 + 35) / 637 = \mathbf{75.4\%}$
Sensitivity	Sensitivity
= $1054 / 1209 = \mathbf{87.2\%}$	= $445 / 517 = \mathbf{86.1\%}$
Specificity	Specificity
= $87 / 283 = \mathbf{30.7\%}$	= $35 / 120 = \mathbf{29.2\%}$

In order to simplify our model, we will perform variable selection, using backward stepwise regression to evaluate a less complex model. The output recommends the removal of the height, weight, BMI and race variables from the model. We have ran a new model with the removal of the suggested variables, that is the model is:

$$Death \sim Age + Sex + Ethnicity \quad (3)$$

The classification from this model on our training and testing sets and the accuracy, sensitivity and specificity of the model are shown in Table ??.

Training Set	Testing Set
Accuracy	
$= (1056 + 82) / 1492 = \mathbf{76.3\%}$	$= (448 + 390) / 637 = \mathbf{76.5\%}$
Sensitivity	
$= 1056 / 1209 = \mathbf{87.3\%}$	$= 448 / 517 = \mathbf{86.7\%}$
Specificity	
$= 82 / 289 = \mathbf{28.4\%}$	$= 39 / 120 = \mathbf{32.5\%}$

4.4.2 Support Vector Machines

Support vector machines is one of the most commonly used classification methods in the literature. A number of different extensions have been introduced in the machine learning literature. One of the most important decisions is to decide which kernel to use. In this work we use Gaussian kernel. The results of the classic SVM algorithm (not presented here) give an overall accuracy of **81.2%** with **100%** sensitivity and **0%**. As with logistic regression before, this is an example where we need to add class weights due to the imbalance in observations between the two classes.

Following the discussion from the previous section about imbalance in SVMs we choose the two costs approach which takes the ratio of the costs as the inverse ratio of the class sizes, that is $\lambda_1/\lambda_2 = n_2/n_1$. We set $\lambda_2 = 1$. In this case then $\lambda_1 = n_2/n_1 \approx 1/4$. These results are in the Table ?? where we can see that there is lower overall accuracy but better specificity in the results.

Training Set	Testing Set
Accuracy	
$= (815 + 198) / 1492 = \mathbf{67.9\%}$	$= (345 + 80) / 637 = \mathbf{66.7\%}$
Sensitivity	
$= 815 / 1209 = \mathbf{67.4\%}$	$= 345 / 517 = \mathbf{66.7\%}$
Specificity	
$= 198 / 283 = \mathbf{70.0\%}$	$= 80 / 120 = \mathbf{66.7\%}$

4.4.3 Decision Trees

We also run decision trees. Similarly to the previous techniques we use weights to address the imbalance. Also to simplify the model we use the reduced model we found in logistic regression after variable selection. In Figure 4, we have a decision tree based upon our Age, Sex and Ethnicity data from the training data set in order to train our decision tree model. The complexity parameter was set to **0.001**, ensuring that features are only added to the tree if they meet the improvement level of at least **0.001**. This is to keep the tree as simple as possible and speed up the search for splits within the data, by acting as a stopping criterion for the algorithm. Each node contains various information: the percentage of the data that lie in that node; the numbers 0 or 1, corresponding to the most likely outcome of survival or death; and finally the probability of the second class occurring, ie. probability of death if the node is predicted to survive or vice versa. The tree in Figure 4 asks a series of questions in order to provide the probability of death for a participant. An answer of ‘Yes’ to a question will lead you down the branch to the left of the node, and ‘No’ will lead you to the right branch. For example, if initially answering ‘Yes’ to node 1 and 2 (Age ≥ 62 and Age ≥ 66), and again ‘Yes’ to node 4 (Ethnicity = Unknown), in which **2%** of the training data set did, then the model predicts the survival probability to be **0.26** or **26%**.

Training Set	Testing Set
Accuracy	
$= (1019 + 136) / 1492 = \mathbf{77.4\%}$	$= (410 + 42) / 637 = \mathbf{71.0\%}$
Sensitivity	
$= 1019 / 1209 = \mathbf{84.3\%}$	$= 410 / 517 = \mathbf{79.3\%}$
Specificity	
$= 136 / 283 = \mathbf{48.0\%}$	$= 42 / 120 = \mathbf{35.0\%}$

Table 2: Results of the classification for Decision Tree with parameter 0.001

As shown in the table the decision tree model predicts the correct classification of the patients with a **71.0%** accuracy but it has a better specificity (at **35.0%**) than the previous methods we have seen.

Figure 5: Simplified Decision Tree

The results in the decision tree can vary on the complexity parameter. Therefore we run also a different decision tree with a complexity parameter set at 0.011. As we can see in Figure 5 the tree starts similarly at the first few nodes and it is much simpler than the previous one. As we can see when we apply this, the overall accuracy has decreased from **71.0%** in our full decision tree, to **67.2%** with the new CP. However, the specificity of predicting those participants who died within the study has increased from **35.0%** in the large decision tree, to now **55.8%**, which is a big improvement.

Training Set	Accuracy	Testing Set
$= (877 + 162) / 1492 = \mathbf{69.6\%}$		$= (361 + 67) / 637 = \mathbf{67.2\%}$
	Sensitivity	
$= 877 / 1209 = \mathbf{72.5\%}$		$= 361 / 517 = \mathbf{69.8\%}$
	Specificity	
$= 162 / 283 = \mathbf{57.2\%}$		$= 67 / 120 = \mathbf{55.8\%}$

Table 3: Results of the classification for Decision Tree with parameter 0.011

4.4.4 Random Forest

Our final method that we will investigate is the Random forest algorithms which is like a decision tree. Increasing the number of trees within the random forest algorithm generally increases the robustness, as well as the accuracy of the results. Training a set of decision trees with the bagging method, the algorithm combines them to build a forest. The bagging method, oth-

erwise known as bootstrap aggregation, is a method used for reducing the variance for algorithm such as decision trees (which usually have large variances). This method works by creating many small subsets of the data and running the decision tree algorithm on them. Then finally, taking the average outcome of all of these small trees as our overall result.

Figure 6: Random Forest Variable Importance

Here, in Figure 6, we have a plot representing the importance of the variables within our random forest. The left hand side plot represents how each variable impacts the accuracy of the model, with a larger value showing to have a more positive improvement on the accuracy. The smaller the *Mean Decrease Accuracy (%IncMSE)* value, the less of an impact that value has on the overall predictability of the model. The *Mean Decrease Gini (IncNodePurity)* on the right hand side, however, looks at how much impact the variables have on the accuracy as well as the misclassification. Both

plots are telling us a similar story, with the *Age* variable having the largest positive impact on the overall accuracy and miss-classification of our random forest model.

When training our model with the training data set we have an Out-Of-Bag Estimate of Error Rate of **20.57%**. This is essentially the proportion of the out of bag samples that were incorrectly classified. We also produced a confusion matrix to understand where this misclassification occurred, for both the testing and training data.

Training Set		Testing Set
Accuracy		
$= (1209 + 232) / 1492 = \mathbf{96.58\%}$		$= (500 + 6) / 637 = \mathbf{79.4\%}$
Sensitivity		
$= 1209 / 1209 = \mathbf{100\%}$		$= 500 / 517 = \mathbf{96.7\%}$
Specificity		
$= 232 / 283 = \mathbf{81.98\%}$		$= 6 / 120 = \mathbf{5\%}$

Table 4: Results of the classification for Random Forests

Here, the model fits our testing data set with an accuracy of **79.4%**, a high sensitivity of **96.7%** and a low specificity of **5%**. Overfitting of the training set may be one reason for the poor specificity of the model on the testing set. This is common for non-parametric models such as random forest and decision trees. To combat this, we have looked into tuning the parameters of the algorithm.

Initially, we have looked at the number of trees included in our random forest model. We have seen that as we increase the number of trees included within our *random forest* model, up to the default of 500, our error generally decreases. However, once reaching 100 trees, the error introduced is no longer significantly reduced, therefore, we will look into changing the number of trees produced for our *random forest* model. We also looked whether changing the value of other parameters will change the results but these had very small effect in the accuracy of the model. This investigation sides well with other researchers who fund minimal improvements when tuning their random forests (see for example P. Probst [22])

5 Discussion

Model	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity	Precision	F1 Score
SVM	81.2%	100%	0%	81.2%	0.896
SVM (weighted)	66.7%	66.7%	66.7%	89.6%	0.765
LR (all variables + weights)	75.4%	86.1%	29.2%	84.0%	0.850
LR (selected variables + weights)	76.5%	86.7%	32.5%	84.7%	0.857
Decision Tree (large)	71.0%	79.3%	35.0%	84.0%	0.816
Decision Tree (small)	67.2%	69.8%	55.8%	87.2%	0.775
Random Forest (not tuned)	79.4%	96.7%	5%	81.4%	0.884
Random Forest (tuned)	79.1%	94.8%	11.7%	82.2%	0.881

Table 5: A comparison of ML model’s performance metrics.

In this work, we use data from the Vivli database to combine data sources for the survival of COVID19 patients based on different physiological characteristics. After treating the missing values, we use four different classification algorithms to build a model for prediction. Although the results as summarized in Table 5 are far from optimal in terms of the accuracy of the prediction we have a good indication. It is interesting to observe that the SVM with the highest accuracy, sensitivity and F1 score is in turn the one with the lowest specificity and precision. The opposite of this can be seen for the pruned decision tree. This may be due to the calculations for precision and F1 score not including the specificity value at all. It is therefore hard to conclude which model would be the most appropriate here. Although ideally the model would predict those who are more likely to die with a high specificity like weighted SVM does, it is also useful to predict those who are more likely to survive with a high sensitivity and high overall accuracy like classic SVM (which, though, has 0% specificity). The weighted SVM have good precision but low accuracy, while the Random Forests have good accuracy and sensitivity but low specificity. On the other hand logistic regression seems to be in between in all the metrics and this may be the best option if we are interested for a good overall performance and not only for a specific metric.

(a) LR (0.711)

(b) LR variable selection (0.717)

(c) SVM (0.627)

(d) weighted SVM (0.667)

(e) Large Decision Tree (0.428)

(f) Small Decision Tree (0.628)

(g) Random Forest(0.717)

(h) Tuned Random Forest(0.709)

Figure 7: ROC Curves and AUC calculation (in parenthesis) for all methods

Another metric that one can use is the ROC curve with a measure of the Area under the curve (AUC) (we include the values in the caption of each figure as it may not be readable on the figure itself). We see from Figure 7 that the highest AUC is given by the weighted Logistic regression after variable selection and the Random Forest.

Overall, this work proves that there is no clear best choice among the different classification algorithms. At the same time, we can see that one of the best choices we have is one of the simplest choices, the simple logistic regression after variable selection. Therefore sometimes, using more complicated algorithms may not necessarily lead to more accurate results.

Appendix

All data for this work has been taken from Vivli, center for global and clinical research data. With the initial data request submitted on 18/08/2021, and complete access approved on 12/11/2021.

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